

SOME UNIQUE PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE FORMATION OF THE STUDENT'S ECOLOGICAL THINKING IN THE TEACHING OF "NATURAL SCIENCE" IN THE 4TH GRADE

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Annotation: In this article, some unique psychological aspects of the formation of the student's ecological thinking in the teaching of "Natural Science" in the IV grade, responsible decision-making in modern complex environmental conditions, adherence to certain didactic principles when determining the content and scope of environmental education, and the formation of environmental competencies in the teaching of "Natural Science" in the IV grade are discussed in this article. focused education is described in detail.

Key words: natural science, ecological thinking, psychological aspects, didactic principles, ecological competence.

Introduction:

The highest product of existence, the image of man is created as an independent, free person who protects himself with his intelligence. Therefore, based on the study of natural phenomena and processes and their rational use for living, spiritual values began to form and develop on the basis of the gradual culturalization and socialization of people. In the early days, education began to be formed in the form of morals and manners for young people, parents' use of nature for living, housekeeping, interaction and nature, but as the scope of knowledge began to expand, the need for special educators began to arise.

In many cases, the concepts of a set of educational rules at the level of a certain tribe, people, and nation were improved by individual people. The primary goal of hygiene education and upbringing in elementary schools is to equip students with basic knowledge of health care, necessary hygiene skills and skills.

Literature analysis and methodology:

Giving information about the stages of correct observance of the student's daily schedule during the course of "Natural Science" lessons in the 4th grade: waking up, physical education, washing, breakfast, going to school, having lunch, rest, preparing lessons, helping with housework, dinner, rest take, go to sleep. The time allotted for these needs to be determined by the child himself, and then he should show the established time standards. It is advisable to organize the topic of personal hygiene: keeping the body and clothes clean, following the rules of nutrition, taking care of the teeth, being careful of colds and infectious diseases, using interactive methods and connecting them with demonstration and practical activities.

"Structure of the human body" in "Natural Science" classes in IV grade. There are many opportunities to provide hygienic education when passing the topics of "Skin, skeleton and muscles, their functions", and it is appropriate to use interactive methods in its delivery.

Learning hygiene knowledge and skills is not limited to study time, but also completed in extracurricular activities. Conversations with students outside of class, discussion of health

issues, morning routines, personal and public hygiene, the importance of physical exercise, etc.

Education and training, these two concepts combined, are like the wings of a bird. Just as a bird cannot fly without one wing, so a student cannot soar. All students in the class have different upbringing and character. Only a skilled and skilled pedagogue can reach the level of a strong psychologist. First of all, the teacher taught the students to think independently, to have the best moral qualities, to be able to connect the knowledge they received with life, to respect the homeland, its history, culture, traditions, and most importantly, to respect the person, scientific outlook, interest in the profession, economic, legal and environmental culture. it is necessary to educate the finder.

A teacher must be a skilled expert in his field, able to find reasonable solutions to problems, constantly creatively work on himself, create innovations, and occupy a worthy place in the hearts of his students. The educational achievements of students are mainly evaluated by the quality of the assignments given to them by the teachers in the educational process, as well as the quality of their professional training.

In the IV class, the science of "Natural Science" has a great influence on the conditions of the social and cultural environment. Ethnic cultural differences differ not only in their way of life, food composition, beliefs, customs and traditions, but also in the relationship of parents to their children. A person is taught to understand and accept the environment, the uniqueness of the environment, through a certain system of the living environment.

In the course of teaching "Natural Science" in the IV grade, the formation of the student's ecological thinking contributes to personal development and self-development, to the subjective feeling of the stability of existence and the harmony of nature. Ecological thinking directs the efforts of people, socio-cultural groups and state bodies to maintain ecological balance, preserve the natural wealth of certain areas, and preserve the nature of the earth as an integral ecosystem for a temporary perspective.

In order to make responsible decisions in modern complex environmental conditions, it is important for a person not only to have deep knowledge in various areas of the environment, but also to have the ability to act in a specific or crisis environmental situation. Based on knowledge, experience, values and inclinations and having environmental competence, this ability of a person requires skill to solve any environmental problems.

In a broader sense, environmental competence corresponds to a person's ability to apply appropriate knowledge and actions to effectively exploit a given environmental situation. Thus, the concept of "ecological maturity" is multifaceted, its content and level depend on many factors: the development of ecology and related sciences, the state of environmental culture, social and economic reasons, certain socio-natural conditions and trends in the interaction of nature and society, and Another characteristic of ecological potential is its actual manifestation in a specific ecological situation.

To be ecologically competent in teaching "Natural Science" in the 4th grade is to skillfully act in a specific ecological situation based on previously acquired knowledge and experience. Environmental competence is a set of interrelated personal qualities necessary for future teachers to preserve the environment. Environmental competence is the ability, readiness and experience of a person to protect the environment and solve environmental problems.

Ecological competence is the ability to apply the theoretical knowledge, practical skills and qualifications acquired in the field of ecology in solving practical and theoretical problems

encountered in everyday life. Competence is pure professional knowledge, skills and abilities, initiative, cooperation, ability to work in a group, communicative ability, ability to realistically evaluate, logical thinking, ability to sort and use information.

In the 4th grade, the education aimed at the formation of environmental competences in the teaching of "Natural Science" is the education aimed at the formation of the competences of practical application of acquired knowledge, skills and qualifications in their personal, professional and social activities. Love of nature is a big and complex feeling. It encompasses the higher realms of the heart and mind and is the main aspect of a person's conscious spiritual life. This feeling corresponds in many ways to patriotism.

Together with the love for nature, love for the country grows in the young generation. It is born directly in childhood, during school years. Growing up and maturing leads to feeling affection and strengthening it. Biological education leads the entire young generation to have a correct attitude towards nature: it educates an impressive love for it, not only to perceive the beauty of nature, but also to protect it, to preserve it, to create and increase natural resources with one's own hands.

Results:

Currently, a new direction in natural sciences has emerged - natural science, based on cybernetics, a technical science based on the structure of living organisms and the processes involved in them, which is a science that connects biology with physics and technology. It can be seen from this that science education in the IV class should have a polytechnic character and should be connected with the participation of the young generation in socially useful and productive work. This connection is carried out in farms, landscaping, searching for new minerals, plants, collecting medicinal plants and other socially useful works. It helps to deepen theoretical knowledge and allows school students related to nature and agriculture to choose a profession.

Studying the science of "Natural Science" in the IV grade gives ample opportunities to cultivate love and respect for work, recognition of work as the source of all material and spiritual wealth of mankind. When the study of natural science course at school is done correctly, it creates and develops the need to constantly update knowledge by obtaining information independently even after graduation.

It is impossible to imagine the life of a modern person without scientific knowledge about living nature, because his life is completely connected with the world of plants and animals. But plants are a source of organic raw materials and energy on Earth. Animal world, in turn, serves as a source of various food and industrial raw materials.

Skillful use of natural resources and their increase serves to increase the welfare of the people and the state. Correctly implemented biological education allows to educate a scientific worldview. Students learn to understand the facts and phenomena of nature in relation to each other, in a state of movement, change and development, while being a natural science education.

Studying the science of "Natural Science" in the IV grade helps in aesthetic education of the young generation in many ways. A wonderful landscape has such an enormous educational effect on the development of a young soul that the influence of a pedagogue cannot be compared with it. In the study of science, aesthetic education is considered as an integral part of the entire educational process. Scientific perception includes aesthetic perception and emotions.

Science has all the potential to positively influence the heart and mind of a person. The perception of nature brings great joy to the person who gets to know it more closely. Providing aesthetic education with natural means helps the general aesthetic education of the young generation.

All this can be achieved only when the laws of nature are deeply and consciously mastered. Dividing students into 4 small groups and achieving high-quality independent performance of educational tasks. The teacher divides the students into groups and directs their activities to independently complete the following tasks.

Discussion:

All the information and knowledge collected by natural sciences in secondary educational institutions cannot be given to students naturally. Accordingly, among them, it is necessary to choose a knowledge study guide that is suitable for the age of students and the current goals and tasks of teaching. The selected knowledge study guide should meet the needs of the state, society, and individual in general secondary education institutions, and should reflect the social, economic and scientific development of the society, and should be mobilized to implement the goals and tasks specified in education.

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Nature conservation is a form of relationship between man and nature, and the preservation, restoration and rational use of the surrounding natural environment, including the Earth's atmosphere, the purity of forests and waters, underground resources, the diversity of flora and fauna, and natural resources. set of measures. In other words, nature protection is a general expression of the system of measures that ensure the ability of natural landscapes to create environments and resources, their diversity, and the preservation of non-renewable resources. In recent years, along with the concept of "nature protection", the concept of "environmental protection" or "environmental protection" has been widely used.

Taking into account that environmental problems are gaining global importance, in recent years, along with important priority tasks, special attention has been paid to the issues of environmental protection, environmental culture, environmental education and environmental enlightenment. "Ecology" is not included as a compulsory subject in the curricula of secondary schools, academic lyceums, colleges and technical schools in our republic. Environmental education is carried out step by step in the family, kindergarten, secondary schools, higher education and post-higher education.

The role of school environmental education is important in students' attitude towards the environment. This education begins in the junior classes when studying the lessons "The world around us" and "Natural science". Through these lessons, students' ideas about the interactions that exist in nature will expand, and on their basis, they will continue to form an ecological worldview and culture, a responsible attitude to the environment and their own health. The school course of natural science has objective opportunities to arouse students' interest in nature, to preserve it, to form and develop moral standards, value orientations.

In the 4th grade, the "Natural Science" course has many priorities compared to other subjects in terms of its ecological orientation, the number and depth of the disclosure of environmental problems, and the justification of ways to solve them. It has a lot of ideas that are a basis for the theory of geoecology and rational use of nature. These ideas are the unity of nature, the interrelationship of all its components and processes, natural complexes, geographical crust, circulation of substances and other ideas. In addition, the natural science course includes many concepts directly related to the theory and practice of rational use of nature, namely, anthropogenic landscapes, global environmental problems, anthropogenic effects on natural resources, the main principles of rational use of nature, and other concepts. In the IV class, in all departments of programs on the science of "Natural Science", attention is paid to the following issues of the ecological plan:

- interaction of humanity and nature in the past and in the present; - the impact of human economic activities on the lithosphere, hydrosphere, atmosphere and biosphere, measures to protect them;
- human activity on soil use and protection, etc.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, it is in the IV class that "Natural Science" is considered one of the fundamental sciences capable of researching and solving environmental problems at the global, regional and local scales. Today's students, that is, the young generation who are the future of our country, should be active participants in solving these problems. Pedagogues have a great role in this process.

The process of ecological education requires a natural science teacher to have a deep understanding of his subject, a skilled master of teaching it, and a perfect mastery of modern innovative technologies. A teacher should know how to follow certain didactic principles when determining the content and scope of environmental education given to students. Pupils should test the theoretical ecological knowledge acquired during the course of the lesson, acquire the skills and abilities to do it, and draw their own conclusions on the problem at hand.

References:

1. Allayorov R.H., Abdukhalikov Q.A., Ergshboyeva M.T., Usmonkhojaeva M.A., "Geography and problems in geography education" Conference, TDPU named after Nizomi, Tashkent-2018.
2. H. Hamidov, A. Hodzhimatov and others. "Ecological culture and spirituality". T., ZUKHRA BARAKA BUSINESS, 2018.
3. Melnikova E.V. Formation of environmental competences of students through project-research activity // Young scientist. - 2015.
4. Sh. Avazov, F. Saydamatov and H. Allaberganov. "Pedagogy" magazine. 2019.
5. Jilbaev.J.O. On the relevance of environmental competence of future specialists // Fundamental research. - 2014..

